

METHOD OF DRAWING THE COMPOSITION OF DIFFERENT STATES OF THE HUMAN BODY IN THE INTERIOR

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Abstract: This article reveals the topic of academic drawing, to display a person in a compositional style in the interior. Academic drawing of people to display in the form of famous artists in a variety of technology.

Keywords: interior view of the room, window, volume, wall, shift, floor, house, decor, plant, view, workshop, library, work, school, coal, sanguine, pastel, technology, style, perspective, light, artificial, bright.

Introduction: It is known from the history, the depiction of interior composition has varied over the centuries. Scientific and practical research has been conducted on the work of great masters of fine arts of the XV century. Leonardo do Vinci wrote a book. We get an idea of the past and present through the design of the interior of the room. It can be seen that the fine arts are used differently in different types and genres.

The most complex and interesting is the depiction in the image that the fine art interior genre pencil perspective interrelates the appearance of the interior with simple and complex objects. Interior (frants.interieur-interior) -1) in architecture - the architectural dimension of the interior (appearance, size, shape, decoration, etc.), depending on the function of the artistically decorated and equipped interior of buildings and structures (residential, public and industrial) Depending on the nature of the equipment (furniture, etc.), the purpose of the building, the creation of a mutually compatible sculpture.

Sitorai Mohi Xosa, Navoi Theater, Peoples' Friendship Palace, Oliy Majlis buildings are different from each other. In Uzbek painting, the interior is an integral part of domestic and historical genre works [12.185].

The interior is used as a background to illuminate the idea of genres of fine arts: still life, portrait, historical, domestic works of art. Through the state of the interior, we can draw conclusions about the taste of the landlord, or about the state of scientific development, depending on the equipment of the factory workshop. We can find out what period the house belongs to through the image of the shape and size of the doors and windows, the walls and ceiling, the decoration of the floor and the decoration of the furniture.

The interior of the theater is aesthetically different from the factory shop with its versatile interiors. Let's imagine a metal foundry shop of the factory. Large slabs laid on the floor of a large workshop, heavy cranes moving on rails, red lava and blue smoke visible from a metal cooking pot next to an artificial light falling through the silver smoke, involuntarily attract the artist with its vital beauty [6.26,27].

Through the works of many artists at different stages of life during the captivity on the subject of the interior, we know the condition of the country houses of that time, the interiors of the palaces. Many such realistic works of art depict the rooms of writers, scholars, and public figures.

The works of the great European masters of fine arts, their contributions to world art in the field of academic penmanship Leonardo do Vinci portrait is a master of scientific and practical pencil and painting. In his works, Linear Perspective uses new techniques in painting to change the dimension of things as they move away from the human eye, that is, to make them appear shorter.

Deep spatial composition - such compositions are mainly used in the design and layout of the interior of public and residential buildings, in particular, hallways, corridors, living rooms, etc. In their works, the texture is derived from Latin and means "structure". It basically means the structure of the top of things. Fakgura is used in the text of the image, emphasizing the smoothness and roughness. Harmony of colors - the

word "harmony" is derived from the Greek and means "connection, harmony". When different colors used in painting are inextricably linked and in harmony with each other, they form a harmony of colors.

Color Contrast (Contrast Colors) - There are inverted types of colors used in painting images. They are light and dark, warm and cold, transparent and dirty, bright and dull colors. They are considered contrasting colors. When two contrasting colors are placed side by side, the brightness of one of them increases and the brightness of the other decreases. This condition is called color contrast. Leonardo do Vinci Interior's composition, pencil and painting works use a variety of scientifically based methods and techniques. The works of Rafael Santi, Rubens Peter Powell, Albrecht Dürer, Titian Vechellio, Rembrand Harmens van Rijn are world famous ones.

The works of great Russian artists, creative activities A.P. Lesenko, A.A. Ivanov, I.E. Repin K. P. Bryullov, OA Kiprenisky, VI Surikov are the founders of the Russian school of fine arts, realistic art education - methodical school. The interior of Repin's painting "Unexpected" depicts the typical lifestyle of advanced intellectuals of the 80s of the XIX century.

All the laws of line and air perspective are followed in the interior. The interior of the room differs in that many objects of different heights and distances are located in the horizontal floor and vertical wall plane. In addition, training on color and "contrast" color solutions, depending on the shade and light conditions.

Based on the history of modern realist fine arts in Uzbekistan, in the early twentieth century, the artist O. Tansiqbaev created the landscape of the painting "Teahouse" in a system of bright colors. Amur Temur, Beruni, Babur, Ibn Sino, Jami and Navoi, Ar-Razi, Al-Khwarizmi, a number of great scholars, poets and statesmen teach the secrets of the work to young people.

Ch.Akhmarov Those in the lobby of the building of the Navoi Opera and Ballet Theater in Tashkent. He created a majestic painting on the events in the epics of Hayratul-ul Abror, Farhod and Shirin, Layli and Majnun, Saddi Iskandariy and Sabai Sayar, which are included in Navoi's famous Hamsa. Whether the main theme is a

myth or an event, the characters, their exact similarity are found in a complex compositional solution. The people in the image are depicted in dimensionally clear lines and light subtle colors. In the way of depicting the human body. [10.95].

Depiction of men and women in national costumes in the works of Rakhim Akhmedov. The human figure, the holistic depiction of light-shadow relationships, body parts, constructive structure. Correct determination of the proportions of body parts. The development of skills in the construction of the body through soft materials, improving the ability to describe the light-shadow relationship as a whole has a special place in the application of methodological methods.

Perform pencil drawings of compositions of different positions of the human body in the interior. A study of coal technique in the depiction of the human body. The works of P.P. Rubens, Leonardo da Vinci, Michelangelo Buonarroti, Rafael Santi, Rubens, Peter Powell, Albrecht Dürer, Titian, Verocchio are the works of Sangina, the methods of applying pastels in the depiction of the body in different positions (sitting, lying).

Michelangelo Buonarroti Michelangelo returned to Florence in 1501. Here, by order of the city council, he began work on his famous "David" statue of solid marble, and finally, in 1504. The statue was erected on the main square of Florence. His contemporaries praised the statue and accepted it as the defender of the Republic of Florence, a symbol of freedom and liberty. In fact, the legendary hero was very reluctant to take advantage of the ideal of the time for the great artist. This image was once addressed by Donatello, Verocchio. But Michelangelo further strengthened his humanistic character by depicting his protagonist's state of being ready for battle, rather than the post-victory period. For the first time in the history of art, he was able to create an image of a brave, powerful man who could fight for his own happiness, appreciate his strength and potential by creating an image of a brave, powerful man who is ready to deal a heavy blow to the enemy. Today, the process of practical training in teaching and drawing is used as a model [10.123].

Albrecht Dürer, the founder of the new genre in Germany, was the first in

Germany to depict the female body in a complex (sitting, lying) position. [3. 251]. By performing the image of P.P. Rubens in the form of light-shadow, falling shadow, students develop skills such as plasticity of the female body, its peculiarities, linear constructive structure, the psychological state of man serves as an aid to students in depiction. Another group of works is the elegantly painted portraits of creative intellectuals, as well as "Dawn", "Motherhood", which is a great example of poetic perception of the world. These works, which are diverse in all respects - social theme, emotional state, style of drawing and approach to nature, amaze with the fact that the human personality is understood from the inside in a unique cultural environment. The portraits belonging to both groups were created with a high sense of empathy that allows us to see and reveal some common features of the national character through originality. Micalangelo, P.P. Rubens, a self-portrait of Isabella, a constructive, perspective, anatomy depiction of the rules, character, beautiful love of the family, delicate woman in a festive dress. the fact that the spouse places the slave on top of the other hand is depicted in the image of the interdependence of deeply human emotions [2.6].

Through thematic performance, the bodies of the two image-makers, standing and sitting, develop students' skills such as composition basics, linear constructive structure, light-shadow relations, laws of perspective, spatial imagination, and psychological state of a person. In the formation of knowledge and skills in human anatomy, charcoal, sanguina, pastel sticks are mostly used in drawing sketches. The composition of the human figure in the interior can deeply express the theme. For example, composition topics such as "School Library", "Gym". In addition, topics such as "Artist's Workshop", "Grandma's Room", "Machine Tuning Workshop" can be given as a final task.

In both cases, it is advisable to first study the interior in detail, make sketches and create an interior composition. The penmanship of the interior is first studied in a sketch, according to the known laws of depiction of the internal appearance of the human body. It is necessary to look closely, the situation in the room, the right choice

of colors.

Our perception of interior perspective; pencil painting, seeing the colors, seeing it uplifting the mood of the interior can be a cozy, festive, how the furniture and furnishings are laid out or under the cold impression. The interior reflects the events and changes in our daily lives.

In short, the development of creative thinking is based on the theme, the development of creative thinking in the fine arts and genres, complex portraits from ordinary still lifes, the historical animal, the vanity, the domestic thematic composition of the human body. The artist depicts the image of the interior in perspective, based on observations, such as our home, library, office, city buildings, museums and so on. The human body is the most complex genre. On the basis of true realism, situations are studied on their own. Before describing the interior, the compositional layout, perspective construction, special long-near cases, comparison of horizontal-vertical sides, and sketch are drawn first. Hundreds of sketches were worked on the work. Our world-renowned great artists have used the technology of handwriting on the basis of variants of various genres, methodical steps. The best option is selected, the technology of drawing is clearly described and reflected in the real fabric. A true work of art is studied over the years in scientific and practical drafts and becomes an original work.

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